

APPLICATION OF RHYTHMIC PERIPHERAL MAGNETIC STIMULATION AFTER SURGICAL TREATMENT OF HERNIATED INTERVERTEBRAL DISCS

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ABSTRACT

To improve the effectiveness of rehabilitation in patients after surgical treatment of herniated intervertebral discs of the cervical, thoracic, and lumbar spine by early incorporation of an innovative method based on the effects of a pulsed magnetic field on the cerebral cortex, spinal nerve roots, peripheral nerves, and muscles into the комплекс rehabilitation program. Materials and Methods: A total of 72 patients were examined and treated at the National Center for Rehabilitation and Prosthetics for Persons with Disabilities during the period from 2023 to 2025. The patients were divided into two groups comparable in age, sex, and major clinical manifestations. Results and Discussion: All patients received comprehensive medical rehabilitation, including pharmacotherapy, physiotherapy, and therapeutic exercise. In addition to comprehensive medical rehabilitation, patients in the main group were prescribed a course of rhythmic peripheral magnetic stimulation. The physiological basis of this method is associated with the effect of induced electric current generated as a result of electromagnetic induction, followed by activation of the conductive structures of the peripheral and central nervous systems. Conclusions: It was found that rhythmic peripheral magnetic stimulation procedures used in rehabilitation after surgical interventions demonstrate effectiveness in the treatment of motor disorders, including central and peripheral paresis, as part of comprehensive therapy.

Relevance: Degenerative-dystrophic diseases of the spine are characterized by a progressive course involving intervertebral discs, joints, ligamentous apparatus, as well as

bone tissue of the spine in the pathological process. The disability rate in this pathology is 4 cases per 100 thousand of the population [1]. One of the manifestations of the degeneration process is the formation of herniated discs, more often as a complication of osteochondrosis. At the same time, different parts of the spine are subject to degenerative changes to varying degrees. Lesions of the lumbosacral, less often the cervical and thoracic spine are relatively more common. Currently, surgical methods predominate in the treatment of herniated discs of the lumbosacral spine (LSS). However, surgery eliminates only one element in the chain of pathological reactions - the compression factor, without leading to the elimination of degenerative and inflammatory processes in the spine, as well as to a change in the neurophysiological characteristics of the root. Inflammatory changes in the compressed root lead to irritation of nerve fibers, impaired microcirculation, intra- and extraneural edema, and axonal degeneration. Clinically, this is manifested by acute or subacute pain radiating to the distal zone of the dermatoma, disorders of pain, temperature and vibration sensitivity (in the form of paresthesias, hyper- or hypoalgesia, allodynia, etc.), a decrease in tendon reflexes, hypotension and muscle weakness innervated by this root [2]. The pain syndrome is mixed in nature - the nociceptive mechanism is associated with irritation of nociceptors in the damaged disk and surrounding tissues, as well as in spasmodic muscles, while the neuropathic component is associated with damage to the nerve fibers of the root due to its inflammation, edema and ischemia. In addition, in patients with a long history of the disease, in most cases, a psychogenic component of pain syndrome is detected [3].

Modern tactics of surgical treatment of intervertebral hernias are aimed at reducing "surgical aggression" and improving the patient's quality of life. However, surgical treatment, even with good direct results, does not exclude the preservation of neurodystrophic changes, as well as relapses of the disease, since it eliminates only the mechanical compression factor [4]. In addition, surgery itself at various levels of the spine due to prolonged mechanical exposure, as a rule, causes irritation and changes in the functional state of the neurovascular segmental bundles and microcirculation of the spinal motor segment rhythmic peripheral magnetic stimulation (rPMS) is currently an innovative promising therapeutic technique for the effect of a pulsed magnetic field on the area of spinal roots, nerves or muscles [5, 11] Peripheral access implies the location of the inductor both in the parietal region of the head, paravertebral or segmental [5, 13], and locally on the muscles of the extremities [10, 14]. The physiological basis of the method is associated with the effect of induced electric current resulting from electromagnetic induction, followed by activation of the conductor structures of the peripheral and central nervous system [5, 8, 9]. The depth of penetration of a magnetic stimulus depends on the power of the magnetic stimulator, the diameter and shape of the inductor (coil). So, with a diameter of 150 mm, with induction on the surface of 1.2 T, the magnetic field power at a depth of 6 cm is 0.2-0.3 T [6]. **(Figure 1).**

Figure 1. Diagram of the cortico-muscular pathway: 1 - central (upper motor neurons) neurons; 2 - source of the facial nerve (peripheral motor neuron of the heart muscle); 3 - corticospinal tract (pyramidal system); 4 - peripheral lower motor neurons (anterior branches of the spinal cord - motor neurons); 5 - narrowed lumbar segment; 6 - narrowed cervical segment; 7 - medulla oblongata; 8 - brain bridge; 9 - corticonuclear pathway; 10 - brain stem

rPMS involves the use of more than 2 stimuli (series) with the same interstimulus intervals [5]. In rPMS, the following parameters are used: stimulus - irritation presented to nervous structures; stimulus intensity (expressed as a percentage of the threshold of induced motor response (IMR)); pack (train) - the selected number of stimuli presented with a given interval; frequency (Hz); pause - time interval between trains; session - duration of stimulation. pSLM with a frequency less than or equal to 1 Hz is considered to be low-frequency, with a frequency from 5 to 25 Hz - high-frequency [5, 12]. The course of treatment, as a rule, consists of a certain number of sessions, the intervals between which can be calculated in hours, days.

Beaulieu L, et al. (2015) provided a review of studies whose main objective was to investigate the significance of rPMS parameters. According to the results of the analyzed works, the most valuable parameters were: inductor shape, train duration, number of stimuli, intensity.

The experience of Russian scientists shows the advantage of using rPMS after surgical treatment of herniated discs of the cervical, thoracic and lumbar spine in the early

postoperative period [7]. 42 patients received rPMS in the early postoperative period together with laser therapy, the other group (42 patients) received electrical stimulation (ES) and laser therapy, the 3 group (20 patients) received laser therapy. Patients of all groups received standard medical therapy. rPMS was carried out with a magnetic field intensity of 0.5 to 1 T, a frequency of 15 Hz, 12 daily sessions.

A significant decrease in the degree of paresis of the extremities was shown in the groups treated with rPMS and ES, and the maximum increase in muscle strength was recorded in patients of the rPMS group. A decrease in pain syndrome was noted in all groups.

Over the past two decades of rPMS research in world practice, certain successes have been achieved in studying the therapeutic effect and mechanism of action of the method. Despite the heterogeneity of the study design and methods for evaluating the effectiveness of rPMS, the concurring results of scientific work indicate the importance of continuing rPMS research in neurological rehabilitation.

The purpose of the study is to increase the effectiveness of rehabilitation of patients after surgical treatment of herniated discs of the cervical, thoracic and lumbar spine by early inclusion in the complex of rehabilitation measures of an innovative technique for the effect of a pulsed magnetic field on the cerebral cortex, spinal roots, peripheral nerves and muscles.

Materials and methods: In the conditions of the orthopedic department for the rehabilitation treatment of patients, examination and treatment of 72 patients in the National Center for Rehabilitation and Prosthetics of Persons with Disabilities for the period 2023-2025. Patients divided into two groups, comparable in age, gender and main clinical manifestations. The criteria for excluding patients from the study were the presence of a pacemaker, decompensated cardiovascular diseases, heart rhythm disturbances, acute infectious diseases, and pregnancy.

Patients by simple randomization were divided into two groups, comparable in age, gender and volume of surgery. Patients in the control group (n = 40) received basic therapy (non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, glucocorticoids, non-narcotic analgesics, antispasmodics, massage and laser therapy). In the patients of the main group (n = 32), in addition to the basic treatment, a course of rhythmic peripheral magnetic stimulation was carried out with Inductors to magnetic stimulators Neuro-MS, Neuro-MS/D manufactured by the Russian company Neurosoft (Ivanovo). During the treatment, patients of the main group received standard medical physiotherapy and rPMS was carried out with a magnetic field intensity of 0.5-1 T, a frequency of 15 Hz, 12 daily sessions (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Equipment overview and transcranial magnetic stimulation procedure. Transcranial magnetic stimulator (Neuro-MS/D) 1 – main unit; 2 – cooling module; 3 – charging module; 4 – inductor bracket; 5 – display and programs

Neurological status, clinical status and ENMG data were assessed in all patients before and after treatment. Also, the WAM (well-being, activity and mood), Oswestry questionnaires were used to confirm the effectiveness of rehabilitation, and methods of assessment according to the NIS scale, JOA, EMS, VAS and methods of statistical analysis were used to assess treatment results

Results and discussion:

In the early postoperative period, patients complained of constant moderate pain in the region of the operated spine with irradiation to the upper and lower limbs (58%), limited mobility in the cervical and lumbar spine (84.2%), sensory disturbances (39%), muscle tone spasticity and the presence of pathological reflexes (37%), a decrease in mood background (49.2%) and increased fatigue (80.4%). Root tension symptoms were reported in 52.1% of cases.

Analysis of the results of repeated examination of the patients of the main and control groups showed that all the examined patients showed positive clinical changes in the form of a decrease or complete disappearance of the pain syndrome, a decrease in muscle tone and severity of pathological reflexes, but the severity of these changes differed. So, in the main group, the complete disappearance of pain syndrome was observed in 66.2% of patients, a decrease in its severity - in 33.8%. The disappearance of muscle tone spasticity and pathological reflexes was observed in 32.4% of patients, while their decrease was observed in 67.6%. In the control group, similar indicators were 54.2% and 45.8%, respectively, for pain syndrome, and the disappearance of spasticity of muscle tone and pathological reflexes was observed only in 12.2% of patients, while their decrease was observed in 87.8%. In addition, a more pronounced regression of symptoms of root tension was observed in the main group, where it occurred on average 4.2 ± 0.3 days earlier compared to the control group.

To confirm the effectiveness of rehabilitation and assess the results of treatment, the WAM (well-being, activity, mood), Oswestry, NIS, JOA, EMS, VAS, as well as ENMG data were used. In both groups, positive unidirectional dynamics was noted, however, a certain

advantage of the rehabilitation complex with the inclusion of rhythmic peripheral magnetic stimulation was revealed for a number of indicators.

Conclusions: Thus, a scientific justification was obtained for the possibility and feasibility of including rhythmic peripheral magnetic stimulation in the complex of rehabilitation measures after surgical treatment of herniated discs of the cervical, thoracic, lumbar and sacral spine. It was found that the use of this method helps to increase the effectiveness of therapy, prevent complications, reduce the duration of neurological deficiency, reduce the severity of muscle tone disorders and pathological reflexes, as well as reduce the risk of disability in patients of this category..

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